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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13693018>**СОЦИОЛОГИЯ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ПРИМЕНЕНИИ К ПРАКТИКЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ
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**SOCIOLOGY OF CULTURE IN RELATION TO THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING A FOREIGN
LANGUAGE****Аннотация.**

Подготовка к межкультурному общению может происходить не только на занятиях иностранным языком, но и через изучение его культуры. Благодаря этому значительно усиливается усвоение многогранной картины мира. Оптимально организованный процесс обучения иностранному языку способен подготовить личность к адекватному и толерантному восприятию чужой культуры, что приводит к нивелированию национальных стереотипов и существующих предрассудков. В результате достигается признание эквивалентности и равенства культур. Признавая актуальность и большое значение лингвострановедческого подхода в обучении иностранному языку в 70-80-е годы, следует отметить, что он недостаточен в современных условиях на рубеже нового тысячелетия. Формирование общечеловеческих ценностей в процессе изучения языка не может быть достигнуто лингвокультурным подходом, который в большей степени имеет познавательную функцию и ориентирован на выявление и демонстрацию чего-то инородного, не присущего родной этнокультуре.

Abstract.

Preparation for intercultural communication can occur not only in foreign language classes, but through the study of its culture. Due to this, the assimilation of a multifaceted picture of the world is significantly increased. An optimally organized process of teaching a foreign language can prepare an individual for an adequate and tolerant perception of a foreign culture, which leads to the leveling of national stereotypes and existing prejudices. As a result, recognition of the equivalence and equality of cultures is achieved. Recognizing the timeliness and great importance of the linguistic and regional approach in teaching a foreign language in the 70-80s, it should be noted that it is insufficient in modern conditions at the turn of the new millennium. The formation of universal human values in the process of language learning cannot be achieved with a linguocultural approach, which, to a greater extent, has an informative function and is focused on identifying and demonstrating something foreign that is not inherent in the native ethnoculture.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, общество, достижения культуры, социология, носитель языка, сотрудничество

Keywords: foreign language, society, cultural achievement, sociology, native speaker, cooperation

Introduction

Among the variety of social processes today, communication plays a leading role as a necessary element of interaction between people, groups, and even entire states. During this interaction, various types of information, meanings, values, assessments, and feelings are transferred and exchanged. The global intellectual internationalization that has engulfed humanity is making the world "transparent". Interpenetration in many aspects of activity makes communication between people closer and cooperation more fruitful. In this regard, the question arises about the preparedness of representatives of different cultural societies for adequate interaction, especially if communication between partners takes place in a non-native language.

The socio-economic and political situation in society forms a social order in relation to the training of its citizens in a foreign language. L.V. Shcherba noted that "the methods of teaching foreign languages in connection with the tasks that society sets for itself at a

given moment, the methodology, depend on the state and structure of this society at a given moment in time. We are talking about the principles of teaching and its systems as a whole, within which all sorts of "methods" and "methods" arise." [Щерба, 1974: 15].

It is quite obvious that the higher the social need for language knowledge and specialists who speak one or more foreign languages, the more significant the pragmatic aspects of teaching the subject become. New professional, personal, cultural, scientific contacts, cultural achievements of different countries provide an opportunity to increase the status of learning a foreign language in public opinion.

Foreign methodologists, along with politicians, use such a concept as "mobility". This means the right of free movement and residence everywhere within the countries that are members of the European Community; the right to be free to receive professional education not only in one's own country, but also abroad, i.e. in neighboring states; a person's ability to adapt to modern living conditions in a multicultural society; the

ability (even at an elementary level) to establish contact with native speakers; the ability to overcome possible difficulties that arise in the process of contact with a foreign culture and its carriers; the ability to show tolerance to someone else's lifestyle and way of life.

The problem of this study is the sociocultural enrichment of the content of teaching English in high schools with in-depth study of the English language.

The purpose of the study is to optimize the process of teaching English in high schools with in-depth study of the English language based on a sociocultural approach through the development of a sociocultural course directly related to the main course of practical classes in English.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve **the following tasks**:

- explore the theoretical foundations for the formation of sociocultural competence;
- explore the socio-psychological prerequisites for the formation of sociocultural competence;
- consider the main methodological provisions for the formation of sociocultural competence;
- to select sociocultural educational material in English for senior classes of schools with in-depth study of the English language.

The object of the study is the sociocultural aspect in teaching English in high schools with in-depth study of the English language.

The subject of the study is the process of developing the sociocultural competence of high school students with in-depth study of the English language on the basis of a specially designed sociocultural course, which provides for the enrichment of students' foreign language practice through the widespread use of sociological and cultural knowledge.

The scientific novelty of the work lies in the fact that:

for the first time an attempt was made to coordinate the use of sociological and cultural knowledge in the methodology of teaching English;

a definition of sociocultural material is given.

Sociology is one of the ways of studying people and their life activities. Sociological scientists strive to find out why people behave in one way or another, why they form certain groups, worship something, demonstrate certain patterns of behavior, choose this or that product, etc. Thus, everything that happens to people when they interact with each other falls into the field of view of sociology. Sociology can be briefly defined as the scientific study of society and social relations. In the process of socialization, from birth, personality is formed, which implies the assimilation of a wide range of values, concepts and expectations, on the basis of which people's daily lives are formed. Education is part of this process where society transfers values, skills, knowledge and abilities from one person or group to another. Education is never the same for all social groups; as long as social stratification exists, education at different levels will be different.

It is believed that initially all children, regardless of their race, nationality, socio-economic status, have the same intellectual abilities to master knowledge. In

many cases, children are hampered by language barriers, insufficient cultural level or low level of training. In some cases, a problem may arise due to a teaching style that is contrary to the behavior patterns that have developed in the minority group. It should also be added that peer groups have a great influence on the formation of students' personality and their success.

The interaction between students who grew up in different ethnic, social and even environmental environments influences the attitudes, behavior and values they acquire. Political and economic conditions determine which of these groups ("professionals," "academics," "collegians," "nonconformists") is the most influential at a given time.

The sociology of culture deals with issues of interaction between various individuals and social groups, which is of particular interest to our research. In order to determine the relationship of the sociology of culture to the practice of teaching foreign languages, it is necessary to consider the concept itself.

Sociology of culture is a new and unstable discipline. At the same time, it is not new in essence. This term was introduced by Alfred Weber at the beginning of the century. However, the sociology of culture cannot be considered a discipline with a stable subject, conceptual apparatus and methodology.

For quite a long time, the sociology of culture was a sociological discipline of secondary importance. This is explained by the specifics of the vision of culture in a social context. Culture was considered something secondary, derived from social processes.

The modern understanding of culture rather rejects the possibility of its existence. The development of ideas about culture and its struggle for "sovereignty", against the ideas of secondaryness, "backwardness" and others took place during the period of postmodernism, and postmodernism rejects the possibility of building such large-scale systems as universal evolution, a universal world system, various global continua, that is, each the social unit will find its place, thanks to which it will be organically included in the overall universal interconnection. The postmodern worldview is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon.

According to L.G. Ionin, in the modern world, development is taking place in the direction of erosion and reduction of the significance of large-scale structural formations, which sociology has traditionally dealt with and continues to deal with [Ионин Л.Г., 1996]. In parallel and at the same time, the role of culture in the regulation of human behavior and in the creation of new structures of a different plan, origin and a different degree of rigidity and objectivity is increasing.

An analysis of the surrounding, everyday reality shows how "cultivated" it is; our lives were filled with cultural contents. Objectively significant systems of stratification have collapsed, compulsory ways of life have disappeared, styles are taking the place of traditions, life forms are freely chosen, postmodernist arbitrariness dominates in explanation, and therefore in behavior. Social change is primarily culturally motivated. All these phenomena indicate that culture is progressively changing along with social development.

The role of culture in society is changing, and the very understanding of culture is changing. This is no longer so much a passive reflection, a copy of real behavioral processes, but rather their active “form”. By “coding” their behavior, correlating it with myth and archetype, individuals consciously use culture to organize and normalize their own activities. Now culture is logically and actually ahead of what is happening in reality. According to the majority of scientists (See, for example, L.G. Ionin, V.A. Yadov), the very subject of science is changing. Western scientist T. Carlyle notes: “Where there used to be “society” ... there has become “culture” [Carlyle T., 1963]. Therefore, science itself is changing, and cultural issues are gradually coming to the forefront of sociological discussions.

Turning to research in the field of sociology of language and interpreting their results for didactic purposes of language pedagogy gradually began to create the basis for the formation and development of such a direction in the methodology of teaching foreign languages as the sociology of teaching and learning second languages. Basically, the emphasis was placed not on the general sociological foundations of language description, which can later be relied upon when describing specific languages of instruction for didactic purposes, but directly on issues of the social context of teaching and learning a foreign language in the formation of a bilingual.

Result

The choice of a foreign language depends not only on the objective needs of society, but also on the personal needs of its citizens. Subjective needs are also determined by the social context in which learning takes place. A person's needs change with age, personal and professional interests. In order to reasonably satisfy public and personal needs in learning a foreign language and prepare students for interethnic communication within the country and abroad, it is necessary to change educational policies regarding foreign languages, supplement educational programs, and also provide for the inclusion of new components in the structure of the content of teaching foreign languages.

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